

D6.3

Dissemination and Communication Plan – final version

WHITE

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SUSTCERT4BIOBASED methodology (GA No. 101059785) for the project's Dissemination and Communication builds on existing expertise, tools and templates developed internally by White Research while also taking into account European Commission guidelines and best practices available in literature. Part of the standard methodology adopted has already been developed in previous research projects where White Research was a beneficiary, such as the INCENTIVE project (GA: 101005330) and ROBIN project (GA: 101060504). This approach ensures optimal resource allocation and adherence to project requirements. Ad hoc and tailored modifications were integrated to the methodology used by SUSTCERT4BIOBASED to comply with GA conditions, EU recommendations and project specificities. This report presents the adjusted methodology as it was further developed and applied within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED.

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ABBREVIATIONS

BMT	BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool
CA	Consortium Agreement
CIRCE	Centro de Investigación de Recursos y Consumos Energéticos
CSL	Certification Scheme and Label
CU	Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH
D&C	Dissemination and Communication Strategy
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
EC	European Commission
ECOS	Environmental Coalition on Standards
EU	European Union
EUBCE	European Biomass Conference and Exhibition
GA	Grant Agreement
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators

NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NoI	Network of Interest
PAB	Project Advisory Board
PC	Project Coordinator
SMA_s	Social Media Accounts
WEcR	Wageningen Economic Research
WFBR	Wageningen Food and Biobased Research
WHITE	White Research SRL
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
WR	Wageningen Research

Executive Summary

This deliverable, ***D6.3 - Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) – Final Version***, provides comprehensive details on all communication and dissemination actions carried out throughout the project and ***outlines measures for continuing dissemination activities beyond the project's completion***. It presents the communication tools and channels which were used to maximise SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's visibility and the overall progress in terms of dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The report outlines the assessment of the dissemination and communication strategy of the project already defined in D6.1 and sets up a detailed monitoring process to ensure the successful continuation of our dissemination efforts.

Most of the chapters included in this report are the final versions of the chapters presented in D6.1, already submitted in November 2022 (M5), and are organised as follows:

Chapter 1: Introduction to the final version of the DCP and its goals. This chapter provides an updated introduction to the dissemination and communication plan (DCP), outlining its objectives and the key strategies adopted to maximise the project's outreach and impact.

Chapter 2: Overview of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project. A brief description of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project, including its goals, scope, and significance in the context of sustainability certification for biobased industrial systems.

Chapter 3: Dissemination and communication (D&C) strategy and its objectives. This chapter presents an updated overview of the project's D&C strategy, detailing its objectives and how they have been achieved and continued after the end of the project.

Chapter 4: Target audience and key messages. An analysis of the project's key stakeholders, engagement strategies, and tailored messages to ensure effective communication and dissemination of project results.

Chapter 5: Tools and channels for dissemination and communication. An in-depth look at the various tools and channels used to communicate and disseminate the project's activities and results, including promotional materials, digital platforms, publications, and events even beyond the project's official timeline.

Chapter 6: Roles and responsibilities. A detailed explanation of the responsibilities assigned to the dissemination manager and consortium partners to ensure the successful implementation of the D&C strategy and the continued dissemination of our project results. The chapter also briefly touches on how these responsibilities may evolve as the project concludes.

Chapter 7: Networks and synergies. This chapter presents our collaborative actions with other relevant projects and networks throughout the project's duration to enhance impact and outreach.

Chapter 8: Monitoring, evaluation, and reporting framework. A presentation of our KPIs used to assess the effectiveness of dissemination efforts, along with an overview of the reporting process for communication activities.

Chapter 9: Timeline and implementation plan. A structured overview of the four different stages of dissemination activities throughout the project's lifecycle, detailing key milestones and how we aim to secure post-project dissemination of results.

Throughout the project, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's communication and dissemination actions reached over 47.000. According to metrics, 5.356 stakeholders were reached through the consortium's efforts to participate in external events, while a significant percentage came from the scientific community, industry and policy area. More than 40.000 stakeholders were engaged through our regular social media posts as our social media campaigns appeared in their feeds. Analysis of the metrics also suggests that the three most effective dissemination channels so far have been: (i) participation in various external events, conferences and online events, (ii) workshops, and (iii) regular social media posts and dissemination of results on the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website. The evaluation of the engagement activities presented in this report clearly indicates that SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's consortium has successfully raised awareness among the targeted stakeholders.

1. Introduction (updated)

This document presents the final version of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED. The DCP served as a strategic framework to effectively communicate the project's vision, objectives, activities, and results to key stakeholders. Since the project's launch, dissemination and communication activities have played a crucial role in raising awareness, engaging relevant audiences, and increasing knowledge exchange between diverse actors. Throughout the project's lifecycle, the strategy has been continuously refined to align with emerging needs and evolving project developments.

This final version of the DCP consolidates the outcomes of our efforts, assesses the effectiveness of the implemented dissemination and communication measures, and provides an operational framework beyond the project. It highlights key dissemination achievements and provides recommendations on how we aim to secure the sustainability of our dissemination efforts beyond the project's end.

Since the beginning of the project, it has been fundamental to disseminate and effectively communicate the project's vision and results to ensure the successful implementation of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED D&C strategy. The main objective of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Strategy presented in D6.1 was to define the actions carried out and the tools to be used for the communication and promotion of the project's results. Indeed, the DCP served as a guiding framework for the consortium's communication and dissemination activities throughout the project's lifecycle.

The dissemination and communication activities were carried out throughout the duration of the project under the dedicated Work Package (WP6 - Dissemination and communication activities). Through multiple and diverse activities, the project aspired to engage a large number of stakeholders who could further spread the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's vision and results to wider audiences through their networks, influence and impact.

Our dissemination activities were carried out in three main directions:

- (i) creating awareness about the project, its vision, and activities;
- (ii) disseminating the project outcomes at local, national and international levels;
- (iii) demonstrating the benefits and maximising impact of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED in order to foster the adoption of our outcomes among interested stakeholders.

The final version of the DCP outlines the impact of our D&C strategy and introduces sustainable measures to ensure the continuation of dissemination activities beyond the project's completion.

2. About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project (updated)

Biobased products are wholly or partly derived from materials of biological origin. Even though they could help reduce greenhouse gas emissions and offer other advantages such as lower levels of toxicity or novel product characteristics (e.g., biodegradability), it is still very important to ensure their sustainability on environmental, social and economic dimensions.

Numerous sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels have been developed to assess and track the sustainability impacts of biobased products. However, the lack of harmonisation among these certification schemes remains a challenge. To address this, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project has played a key role in defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels. By doing so, the project has laid a strong foundation for accelerating and facilitating a smoother transition toward a circular and sustainable bioeconomy.

The project has achieved this by operationalising its tasks and developing the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT), a tool to evaluate the effectiveness and robustness of existing certification schemes and labels. The team has also assessed the feasibility of adopting these certification schemes and labels by considering both costs and benefits, including internalised environmental and social factors. The project's results, along with insights gained throughout its implementation, have been used to provide tailored recommendations to four key target groups:

- ❖ Policymakers;
- ❖ The sustainability system community;
- ❖ Industrial biobased value chain actors;
- ❖ Regional bioeconomy stakeholders.

Therefore, reiterating the project's objectives, we can state that the project manage to achieve the below objectives and:

- ✓ **Reviewed and analysed existing international and EU sustainability certification schemes** and business-to-business labels for biological resources, as well as for biobased materials and products.

Relevant activities: [D1.2 – Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels \(submitted\)](#)

- ✓ Created a **database of global trade flows** for biological resources and biobased materials and products, distinguishing between certified and uncertified products.

Relevant activities: [D2.2 – Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased products \(submitted\)](#)

- ✓ **Developed a monitoring framework** for systematically evaluating the effectiveness and robustness of existing sustainability schemes and labels.

Relevant activities: [D3.3 – Description of the monitoring system \(to be submitted by M36\) \(submitted\)](#).

- ✓ **Applied the developed monitoring framework** to assess existing schemes and identify the “best-in-class” among them.

Relevant activities: D3.2 – Evaluation of existing schemes and labels (submitted).

- ✓ Assessed the costs and benefits of adopting certification schemes and labels in selected industrial biobased value chains.

Relevant activities:

D4.1 - Review of methodologies for cost-benefit analysis and internalizing externalities for sustainability certification (submitted)

D4.2 – Selection of biobased value chains for cost-benefit analysis (submitted)

D4.3 – Data collection template for cost benefit analysis (submitted)

D4.4 – Assessment of feasibility of certification adoption in selected value chains (submitted)

- ✓ Identified best practices and provided recommendations for the adoption of effective and robust sustainability schemes and labels.

Relevant activities:

D5.2 - Mid-term policy brief (submitted)

D5.3 - Final policy recommendations (submitted)

D5.4 - Thematic briefs laying down recommendations to scheme/label owners and standards writers (submitted)

D5.5 - Thematic briefs to industrial biobased value chain actors (submitted)

D5.6 - Thematic briefs to regional bioeconomy actors (submitted)

- ✓ **Engaged a variety of relevant stakeholders**, including international organisations, industrial parties, scheme owners, certification bodies, and policymakers.

Relevant activities:

All consortium activities under WP1–WP7 involved various stakeholders in both scientific and engagement activities, contributing not only to the implementation of the project but also to the dissemination of its results. Workshops within the different WPs, engagement events under Task 6.2, Network of Interest events, establishment of the Advisory Board, and participation in research activities and other dissemination events all supported the communication of our message beyond the project.

During the project's grant period (June 2022 to May 2025), the multidisciplinary SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium achieved these objectives and organised several events and workshops to inform the audience about key findings and project updates. However, sustainability remains central to the project's goals, particularly in ensuring the continued dissemination of its results. Maintaining multiple communication channels to leverage the project's assets is a key priority for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED.

3. Dissemination and communication strategy (updated)

3.1 Overview (updated)

The initial DCP of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED described the overall D&C strategy of the project regarding the project’s outcomes and the dissemination and communication of them. The D&C strategy was carefully designed and tailored to align with the project’s approach, ensuring maximised impact, knowledge transfer, and effective engagement with the targeted stakeholders. It also aimed to communicate the project’s concept to a wider audience. This D&C strategy was then translated into an actionable plan by considering multiple key elements, as illustrated in **Figure 1** below and described in D6.1, the initial version of this Deliverable.

Figure 1. Overview of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’s D&C strategy

The following chapters and sub-chapters outline the outcomes of our D&C strategy, evaluating the effectiveness of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED’s outreach efforts. They also highlight the key assets developed throughout the project and illustrate how these assets effectively convey our core messages.

To ensure the continued dissemination of our results beyond the project’s duration, the final version of the DCP serves as a strategic guidance document, offering recommendations for sustaining engagement and maximising the long-term impact of our findings.

3.2 Objectives of the DCP – how they were achieved and follow – up actions (new)

The D&C strategy of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED set a list of practical and realistic objectives that ensured the effective monitoring and consequently the successful implementation of the

dissemination and communication activities of the project. These objectives answered the question of WHY the DCP was needed and, as outlined in D6.1, are briefly presented below:

- Present the project's aim, vision, activities and events to a wider audience;
- Promote awareness raising among stakeholder groups;
- Encourage involvement in the project's activities;
- Engage stakeholders through a series of relevant activities, events and conferences;
- Ensure that the key messages are communicated to its target audiences;
- Ensure the exploitation of the project's outcomes;
- Introduce scientific concepts in an easy-to-grasp way to stakeholders and citizens;
- Plan, organise, run, monitor and fine-tune the project's dissemination activities and events;
- Establish and sustain synergies with other relevant national and European projects and networks;
- Disseminate the project's lessons learnt and outcomes in an open and transparent way;
- Establish an active community exchanging ideas and knowledge on topics relevant to the project (e.g., sustainability certifications for biobased systems).

Following the project's completion, these objectives have been successfully achieved. The table below provides an overview of how the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project achieved its key dissemination and communication objectives. Through a combination of targeted outreach, stakeholder engagement, and knowledge-sharing activities, the project ensured maximum communication impact and long-term sustainability. Each objective was addressed using specific strategies and actions, as outlined in the table below. Looking ahead, the strategies and lessons learned will continue to inform future dissemination efforts, allowing the project's results to remain accessible and relevant to key stakeholders and audiences.

Table 1. Key dissemination and communication objectives – how they were achieved and follow-up actions

Objective	How it was achieved	Future sustainability & follow-up actions
<i>Presenting the project's aim, vision, activities, and events</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developed and maintained a project website serving as a central hub for information. Created informative brochures, newsletters, and videos to highlight the project's goals and achievements. Established Social Media Accounts (SMAs) (LinkedIn, YouTube, etc.) to reach a broad audience. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The project website will remain live and accessible post-project, acting as a central repository for all project outputs, documents, and key findings. The brochures, newsletters, and videos will remain available for download on the website, ensuring that the materials are accessible for new stakeholders or external parties. Additionally, these can be shared with future projects, organisations, or networks to spread the project's results further. Social media accounts (LinkedIn, YouTube, etc.) will continue to be open by the project partners or associated stakeholders.
<i>Promoting awareness raising among stakeholder groups</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conducted Network of Interest (NoI) meetings and organised events and workshops to spread knowledge on sustainability certifications for biobased systems. Published deliverables on the website, articles and policy briefs, to inform policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers. Engaged with stakeholders through newsletters and direct communication channels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Network of Interest (NoI), even after the project's completion, can continue to function through online channels such as LinkedIn. All publications (deliverables, articles, and policy briefs) will remain available on the project website, with open access for ongoing reference. All project deliverables are uploaded to Zenodo.
<i>Encourage involvement in the project's activities</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Circulated open calls for participation in project surveys and our NoI. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not applicable after the end of the project.

Objective	How it was achieved	Future sustainability & follow-up actions
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fostered collaboration with industry partners such as multiple sustainability Certification Schemes and Labels (CSLs), and policymakers and engaged all project partners. 	
<p><i>Engage stakeholders through relevant activities, events, and conferences</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-organised three engagement events, Network of Interest (NoI) meetings with a different thematic focus, hosted panel discussions during the engagement events, and networking sessions. Hosted co-creation workshops to involve stakeholders in receiving feedback. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> While formal dissemination events (such as workshops or conferences) will no longer be organised, stakeholders involved in the project will be encouraged to continue sharing project results in their networks voluntarily.
<p><i>Ensure key messages are communicated to target audiences</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developed a targeted communication plan with tailored messages for different stakeholder groups. Ensured clear and consistent messaging across all communication channels. Used visual material to enhance message clarity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The visual materials created during the project will continue to be available for download or sharing through the project website and related social media channels. These resources can be used by other organisations, projects, or networks to communicate key messages clearly, ensuring that the visual elements of the project remain part of future outreach activities in the field.
<p><i>Ensure the exploitation of the project's outcomes</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developed an exploitation strategy to facilitate the uptake of project results. Provided policy recommendations through policy briefs. Engaged with standardisation bodies and CSLs to translate findings into practice. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The policy briefs will remain accessible on the project website for future reference. They can be shared with policymakers and stakeholders in related fields, ensuring that policy recommendations continue influencing future regulations. Standardisation bodies and CSLs can reference the project's findings when revising standards or

Objective	How it was achieved	Future sustainability & follow-up actions
		<p>certifications. The project's final reports and deliverables will be shared with these bodies to ensure that the lessons learned are considered in future initiatives or updates.</p>
<p><i>Introduce scientific concepts in an easy-to-grasp way to stakeholders and citizens</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Used plain language in the project's promotional video to simplify complex concepts. • Developed interactive content and animated presentations. • Provided training materials and guides for non-expert audiences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The promotional video and other simplified resources will remain accessible via the project website and social media platforms. • The project's webinars will remain available for download and can be shared with organisations or future projects to continue supporting non-expert audiences.
<p><i>Plan, organise, run, monitor, and fine-tune dissemination activities</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implemented a structured dissemination plan with measurable KPIs. • Conducted continuous monitoring and impact assessment of outreach efforts. • Adapted strategies based on stakeholder feedback and engagement analytics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As part of the project's final phase, a strategy for the future exploitation and dissemination of results has already been developed. This includes ensuring that the project materials, key findings, and resources are accessible to stakeholders for continued use.
<p><i>Establish and sustain synergies with other relevant national and European projects and networks</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborated closely with EU-funded projects and initiatives working on related topics. • Co-organised and participated in joint events, posted/reposted relevant content and published synergies on the website. • Shared best practices with other EU-funded projects and policy forums. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The synergies established with national and European projects will continue to be valuable even after the project concludes. The project's results and lessons learned will remain accessible to these networks, enabling future collaborations. Relevant parties can use the established contacts and partnerships to integrate the project's outcomes into

Objective	How it was achieved	Future sustainability & follow-up actions
		<p>their work, ensuring that the project’s impact is sustained within these broader networks</p>
<p><i>Disseminate project lessons learned and outcomes in an open and transparent way</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disseminate the project’s findings, lessons learned and project outcomes. • Published open-access research results, scientific papers, and policy briefs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The lessons learned and project outcomes will remain accessible to all through the project’s website and open-access publications as well as through Zenodo.
<p><i>Sustain the project’s impact through open access and community building</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster the establishment of the Network of Interest’s community for long-term knowledge exchange. • Established a joint LinkedIn page for stakeholders interested in Certification and Labelling Schemes for the EU bioeconomy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Though the project ends, the LinkedIn group will serve as a space where stakeholders can continue to interact, share new developments, and discuss the future of certification schemes for the EU bioeconomy.

4. Target audience and key messages (updated)

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED enhanced the sustainability certification of the bio-based products sector by engaging key stakeholders, including policymakers, bio-based industry players, certification bodies, researchers and other EU-funded projects. By initiating dialogues, forming collaborations with other actors, and raising awareness, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promoted the adoption of credible and transparent sustainability certification schemes, supporting the transition towards a more sustainable bio-based economy.

4.1 Target audience & engagement measures

One of the most critical steps in developing the D&C strategy in D6.1 was identifying the project’s target audience, meaning the key stakeholders the project aims to engage and communicate its messages and results to. This question was addressed, and in **Figure 2**, we present the main target audiences that SUSTCERT4BIOBASED has reached throughout its lifecycle. Additionally, we present how we engaged them and the key assets created.

Figure 2. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED target audiences

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED engaged a wide variety of stakeholders with different backgrounds and experiences. Table 2 below presents our target groups and engagement measures throughout the project’s duration.

Table 2. Target groups and engagement measures

Target Group	Sub-categories	Engagement measures	Beyond the project
Sustainability system actors	Scheme/Label owners Standardisation bodies Certification bodies	Direct consultations and co-creation workshops, engagement in sustainability certification discussions.	Continued access to published project reports and results through the project's website, Zenodo accounts and possible follow-up discussions through partners' networks and knowledge exchange.
Policy actors	EU policy-makers Policy advisors Governments	Policy dialogues during our engagement events, the project's deliverables, workshops, Nol meetings & Nol interview Series, and policy briefs to support informed decision-making on certification schemes for industrial bio-based systems.	Project findings will be referenced in future policy discussions, publications, or reports that remain publicly accessible.
Industrial actors	Industrial biobased value chain actors Biomass producers Industrial operators and traders	Direct consultations and engagement during our engagement events, workshops, Nol meetings and Nol Interview Series, posts on our SMAs, and participation in our panel discussions.	Industry stakeholders will continue to have access to project results and publications through the website and Zenodo.
Regional bioeconomy stakeholders	Local authorities Farmers Unions Entrepreneurs	Engagement through events, workshops, Nol meetings, and posts on our SMAs.	Continued access to project resources via digital platforms, and potential future opportunities for engagement through public events.

Target Group	Sub-categories	Engagement measures	Beyond the project
Scientific community	Research Centres Research groups Individual researchers Universities	Knowledge exchange through scientific publications, Nol meetings, Nol Interview Series, engagement events and presentations at the European Biomass Conference (2024, 2025).	Future collaboration or networking may take place through scientific publications, conferences, or informal knowledge exchange platforms.
NGOs	NGOs	Engagement through the project's deliverables and scientific publications, Nol meetings, Nol Interview Series, workshops and engagement events.	Ongoing access to project findings via reports and publications, with potential follow-up at relevant workshops or events on sustainability and bioeconomy topics.
International organisations	International organisations Platforms for international cooperation	Direct consultations and co-creation workshops, Nol meetings, engagement in sustainability certification and ecolabelling discussions.	Continued access to project results and engagement via publication
Relevant EU projects & initiatives	Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects Other European and national projects.	Networking events, knowledge exchange through scientific publications, Nol meetings, Nol Interview Series, engagement events, and presentations at the European Biomass Conference (2024, 2025).	Project outcomes will remain accessible through our established synergies, publications, and the potential for further collaboration, especially within the cluster group, will be explored.
Society	General public Civil society organisations	Public awareness campaigns, online publications on our website, and social media engagement through our posts to inform and educate the general public about bio-based products and sustainability certification-related research topics.	Ongoing access to project materials and findings through the project website and public reports, as well as through the LinkedIn group page.

4.2 Key messages and vision (updated)

Another important step in establishing a successful D&C strategy in D6.1 was determining **what** would be communicated to stakeholders. The key target audiences consisted of stakeholders with diverse backgrounds and needs, requiring tailored messages for effective communication. We leveraged the extensive network of consortium partners to reach a wide pool of stakeholders and communicated our messages to them. However, as mentioned in D6.1, the key messages were defined throughout the project's lifecycle based on the actual SUSTCERT4BIOBASED data and outcomes. The table below presents the messages and how we group them with the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED developed assets.

Table 3. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED target audience, needs and messages

Target Group	Needs	Messages	Assets that communicate our messages and will continue to do so
Sustainability system actors	<p>To enhance the adoption of their certification schemes/labels in the market.</p> <p>To increase the credibility of their certification scheme.</p> <p>To keep certification standards up to date based on scientific research findings.</p> <p>To engage with the certification community.</p> <p>To exchange best practices on the improvement of the certification process.</p> <p>To explore synergies and collaboration.</p>	<p>The potential opportunities for improvement of their schemes.</p> <p>How to increase the adoption of effective schemes.</p> <p>How to enhance the credibility of their schemes.</p> <p>Provide a network with other actors who are active in the field of certification for further collaboration.</p>	<p>➔ Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems.</p> <p>➔ BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT).</p> <p>➔ Results from testing of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool on selected certification schemes and labels.</p> <p>➔ Recommendations to standards writers, scheme owners, and certification bodies.</p> <p>➔ Network of Interest</p>
Policy actors	<p>To understand the current landscape of biobased value chains and the extent of their certification.</p> <p>To monitor the progress in the field of biobased economy certification systems and support their harmonization.</p> <p>To have actual data and consistent information on the current developments in the certification field.</p>	<p>How to incorporate certification schemes into policy measures.</p> <p>Provide data and figures on trade of the biological resources and biobased materials and their level of certification.</p> <p>How can the monitoring system be integrated into the policy process.</p>	<p>➔ Quantification of global trade flows of selected biobased value chains.</p> <p>➔ BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT).</p> <p>➔ Methodology for cost-benefit analysis and internalising externalities for sustainability certification.</p> <p>➔ Recommendations to policymakers.</p>

Target Group	Needs	Messages	Assets that communicate our messages and will continue to do so
Industrial actors	<p>To get clear information on the existing certification schemes/labels.</p> <p>To understand the costs and benefits of the adoption of certification schemes/labels.</p> <p>To stay competitive and be considered credible.</p> <p>To enhance sustainable production.</p>	<p>Information on the existing schemes/labels and, in particular, the best-in-class examples.</p> <p>Information on the costs and benefits of the adoption of certification schemes.</p> <p>Creation of cross-sectoral dialogue and trust.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems. ➔ Identification of the most prominent biobased value chains in the EU. ➔ Assessment of feasibility of certification adoption in selected value chains. ➔ Recommendations to industrial biobased value chain actors. ➔ Network of Interest.
Regional bioeconomy stakeholders	<p>To improve sustainability and protect rural areas.</p> <p>To get insights on more sustainable practices and certification schemes.</p> <p>To engage more in circular economy practices.</p> <p>To make their products more sustainable.</p>	<p>Ways to integrate identified recommendations into regional bioeconomy strategies</p> <p>Information on the existing schemes/labels</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Classification of biological resources and biobased products. ➔ Evaluation of existing schemes and labels ➔ Recommendations to regional bioeconomy actors. ➔ Network of Interest.
Scientific community	<p>To keep up with recent developments and research trends.</p> <p>To develop research practices in the fields of bioeconomy and certification processes.</p> <p>To identify research gaps for further research.</p>	<p>New research findings along with their importance for the scientific community.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT). ➔ Methodology for cost-benefit analysis and internalising externalities for sustainability certification. ➔ Scientific publications and research collaborations.

Target Group	Needs	Messages	Assets that communicate our messages and will continue to do so
NGOs	<p>To stay updated regarding the latest trends in the sector.</p> <p>To have access to results regarding the benefits of the adoption of certification schemes.</p> <p>To engage and inform more citizens about sustainable bio-based products.</p>	<p>The positive impact of the adoption of certification schemes and labels on the industry, the local community and the environment.</p> <p>Ways to integrate the best practices derived from the project to ensure sustainability of biobased products</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems. ➔ Evaluation of existing schemes and labels. ➔ Assessment of feasibility of certification adoption in selected value chains. ➔ Recommendations to regional bioeconomy actors. ➔ Network of Interest.
International organisations	<p>To stay informed about the progress regarding the adoption of sustainability certifications for bio-based systems.</p> <p>To have access to data regarding the benefits of the adoption of sustainability certification schemes.</p>	<p>Information on the performance of existing schemes and labels</p> <p>Data regarding the cost and benefits of the adoption of sustainability certification schemes.</p> <p>Data on the global trade flows for biological resources and for biobased materials and products (distinguishing between certified and uncertified).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Evaluation of existing schemes and labels. ➔ Assessment of feasibility of certification adoption in selected value chains. ➔ Quantification of global trade flows of selected biobased value chains. ➔ Recommendations to policymakers and certification bodies. ➔ Network of Interest.
Relevant EU projects & initiatives	<p>To exchange knowledge with other experts in the sector.</p> <p>To share their results and promote their concept to other initiatives and the general public.</p> <p>To establish synergies and expand their network.</p>	<p>Deliverables with the project results to enhance their further research in the sector.</p> <p>A network of synergies that facilitates the dialogues and the collaborations between the relevant initiatives.</p> <p>Support in the dissemination of the project's results.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ Scientific publications and project deliverables. ➔ Network of Interest. ➔ Short brochure with project results. ➔ Website secured for post-project visibility. ➔ Zenodo repository for open-access research.

Target Group	Needs	Messages	Assets that communicate our messages and will continue to do so
Society	<p>Increase awareness of the products with sustainability certifications.</p> <p>To inform about bio-based products.</p> <p>To inspire citizens to make sustainable and circular choices.</p>	<p>Increased engagement of citizens in more sustainable and biobased practices.</p> <p>Interesting findings from the project's results about the benefits (social, economic and environmental) of the adoption of sustainability certification schemes.</p>	<p>→ Scientific publications and project deliverables.</p> <p>→ Network of Interest.</p> <p>→ Short brochure with project results.</p> <p>→ Website secured for post-project visibility.</p> <p>→ Zenodo repository for open-access research.</p>

4.3 Key assets (new)

After 36 months of collaborative work, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED team has produced multiple **key assets**. Specific assets were identified in the proposal phase and were included in D6.1 – Dissemination and Communication Plan – Initial version. The final assets that emerged are presented below:

- **Classification of biological resources and biobased products;**
- **Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems;**
- **Identification of the most representative biobased value chains in the EU;**
- **Quantification of global trade flows of selected biobased value chains;**
- **BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT);**
- **Results from testing of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool on selected certification schemes and labels;**
- **Methodology for cost-benefit analysis and internalising of externalities for sustainability certification;**
- **Data collection template for cost and benefit analysis;**
- **Recommendations to policymakers;**
- **Recommendations to standards writers, scheme owners and certification bodies;**
- **Recommendations to industrial biobased value chain actors;**
- **Recommendations to regional bioeconomy actors;**

4.4 Dissemination of our key assets (new)

Ensuring the continued dissemination and application of these assets will support industry stakeholders, certification bodies, and regional bioeconomy actors in making informed decisions. This strategy focuses on targeted communication activities to ensure the long-term adoption of our BMT and other research resources produced within the project's lifecycle. With the below-targeted actions, we aim to secure the sustainability of our assets.

Post-project Dissemination Actions

- **Website:** Maintain the project's [website](#) for **4 years** after the completion of the project to facilitate knowledge sharing and uptake of our research results.
- **Maintain a Zenodo account:** Zenodo provides free and permanent storage for research outputs, ensuring that datasets, reports, and publications remain accessible to the research community. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED maintains a Zenodo account ([here](#)) and uploads all public deliverables and datasets produced within the project. This contributes to sustaining SUSTCERT4BIOBASED knowledge sharing and preventing data loss over time.
- **Network of Interest:** Invited them to join the LinkedIn group we jointly created ([Certification and Labelling Schemes for the EU bioeconomy](#)) with our sister projects [3CO](#) & [BioReCer](#). The **Certification and Labelling Schemes for the EU Bioeconomy** LinkedIn group will be maintained and sustainably working as a hub for stakeholders interested in sustainability certification-related topics and events organised from related Horizon Europe projects in the future. Our Nol members who will potentially join the group will stay updated about future developments in the sector and have the opportunity to learn more about the most recent event updates.
- **Policymakers:** Provide policymakers who have collaborated in our events and co-creation workshops with policy recommendations and share the final version of the BMT Excel that will be available on our website and Zenodo account. Also, the newly developed web-tool of the BMT will be made available (temporarily hosted on the STAR4BBS website – it will be integrated into our website, which may later redirect users to the web-based BMT link).
- **Standard writers, CSLs & Standardisation Bodies:** Maintain engagement with CSLs, standards writers, and certification bodies through our published deliverables, the BMT, and invite them to the LinkedIn group to stay informed about policy developments. Additionally, the project coordinator, as a member of the CEN Technical committee 411 on biobased products continues communication of the project findings to the standards writers.
- **Industrial biobased value chain actors:** Share with our Nol industrial actors the BMT tool and website link, and provide them with industrial recommendations through our website and the Zenodo repository.
- **Regional bioeconomy actors:** Provide our Nol regional bioeconomy actors with recommendations to regional bioeconomy actors through our website and the Zenodo repository.

Data Accessibility & Open Knowledge Sharing

- **BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT):** With our open-access tool, which is available **as a publicly accessible Excel-based tool** on our website and Zenodo and soon also to be available as a web-based Tool (temporarily hosted on the STAR4BBS website), we provide policymakers with long-term support for enhancing transparency and evaluation of existing sustainability certification schemes and labels (CSLs) for biobased systems, assessing their

contribution to EU sustainability goals, and exploring their role in co-regulation. We also provide long-term support to CSL owners when identifying gaps and weaknesses to improve certification systems and support harmonisation through shared sustainability and governance criteria.

- **Open-source Methodologies:** Ensure that the methodologies developed within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED (e.g., cost-benefit analysis) and data templates will remain publicly available on our Zenodo account and adaptable for other researchers.

Collaborations & Partnerships

- **Scientific & Industry Collaborations:** Maintain cooperation with Wageningen Research communication department to upload relevant BMT articles.
- **EU & International Networks:** Upload to EuBioNet an article about the final conference.

Media & Public Outreach

- **Social Media:** Maintain all project's SMAs and pin a post about the BMT and the final research outcomes of the project.

5. Communication and dissemination tools and channels

As outlined in the initial version of the DCP, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED deployed multiple tools and channels in order to ensure that activities and produced outcomes reached a wide variety of stakeholders. Below is an overview of the different tools, channels and planned dissemination activities that showcase **HOW** the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED D&C strategy was implemented.

Figure 3. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's communication activities

SUSCTCERT4BIOBASED's promotional material and graphical identity include:

- Project's logo
- Project's visual and graphical identity
- Trifold leaflet
- Poster
- Presentation template
- Publication template
- Letterheads
- Promotional video
- Ad-hoc promotional material (e.g., updated poster)

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's online presence includes:

- Website
- Bi-annual Newsletter
- Facebook page
- X account
- LinkedIn profile
- YouTube channel

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's events include:

- Engagement events
- Final dissemination event
- Workshops
- Network of Interest meetings

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's publications include:

- Project's deliverables
- Scientific publications
- Other publications (e.g., articles, press releases, etc.)

The following sub-chapters present a detailed description of the abovementioned tools and channels.

5.1 Promotional material

The promotional material of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED was prepared during the early stages of the project. WHITE was responsible for the graphic design and the content, while the consortium partners offered feedback throughout the development process. The material has been made freely available for download to the public on the project's website [here](#), as well as on SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's SharePoint repository, so that partners can download, print and distribute them when needed. All promotional materials were used during physical activities (including external and project events) to attract and engage relevant stakeholders and provide more information on the project's mission and objectives.

All the promotional material was designed based on the project's unique identity, which is presented in the following sub-chapter.

Beyond the Project

Although the project's active dissemination phase is concluding, the promotional materials remain a valuable resource that can continue to be utilised in future collaborations, outreach efforts, and related initiatives. As the project website is expected to stay online for 4 years, the downloadable materials will remain accessible to stakeholders, enabling further sharing and dissemination beyond the project's formal end.

5.1.1 Project logo

The early design of the graphical identity of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED in terms of the project’s logo and templates ensured consistency throughout the project. The project’s logo and visual identity have already been developed (M1) to satisfy the visual requirements of the project. The logo made the project recognisable and formed the basis for the design of all the promotional materials, which were used for the different promotional and communication materials (e.g., leaflets, posters, newsletters, deliverables, social media, website, publications, publicity for internal and external events, etc.). After internal discussions - and with the agreement of all partners - the final logo was selected (more information in D6.2: SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional package). The final logo is presented below:

Figure 4. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project logo

Figure 5. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED color palette

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED logo should be visible to all the communication material produced in the framework of the project (presentation, deliverables, etc.). Similarly, the EU funding should be properly acknowledged, and the EU emblem should also be properly depicted in all communication material.

Figure 6. EU funding statement

5.1.2 Leaflet and poster (updated)

A trifold leaflet and a poster (presented in D6.2: SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional package) were prepared to be distributed by the partners in physical events and activities, but also to be uploaded on the project’s website. Both the poster and leaflet were used to attract stakeholders’ attention and provide brief information about the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project.

The leaflet presents the project’s aim to fill the research gap on the harmonisation of certification schemes, its vision and its impact, as well as the stakeholders who benefited from the project’s

outcomes. The poster focuses more on attracting the stakeholders’ attention with graphical elements and offers some basic information on the project and the key stakeholder groups.

Both items provide information about the partners involved, together with their contact details, website and SMAs, as well as acknowledging the funding the project receives through the Horizon Europe program.

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website visitors could easily download the leaflet and the poster.

Figure 7. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED leaflet

Figure 8. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED poster

For the needs of our 1st cluster engagement event and workshop on Sustainability certification of bio-based products within the framework of EUBCE 2023 (6 June 2023), WHITE updated the poster to better reflect the project’s approach.

Figure 9. Updated SUSTCERT4BIOBASED poster

5.1.3 Publication templates

Besides the poster and the leaflet, templates (presented in D6.2: SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional package) have also been prepared in line with the graphical identity of the project to be used during dissemination activities. The developed templates include:

- The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED **presentation template** (used by the consortium partners during events and meetings)
- **Reports template** (used for the project’s deliverables and other publications)
- **Letterheads** (used for official invitations to events)

Figure 10. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED ppt and report template

All partners used the official project templates when preparing presentations or reports in the framework of the project.

5.1.4 Letterhead

In addition to the abovementioned templates, and as part of the promotional materials prepared, WHITE provided a letterhead to be used for official invitations to various project activities.

Figure 11. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED letterhead

5.1.5 Promotional video (updated)

The promotional video of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project was produced in June 2023 (M12) to present the project, its objectives, and expected outcomes briefly and animatedly. The video creation process followed a structured approach. First, a video script was prepared, including the sequence

and key phrases explaining the project’s objectives, sustainability certification aims, and approach. All partners provided feedback to improve the script. After incorporating their comments and suggestions, the initial storyboard was ready. Following another round of feedback and refinements, the final storyboard was completed, leading to the production of the animated video.

The video aimed to reach a broad audience through social media networks and online platforms. It has been uploaded to the project’s YouTube channel [here](#), the project’s website [here](#), and shared across all SUSTCERT4BIOBASED SMAs. Additionally, it has been promoted during both our physical and digital events. Its purpose is to introduce the project clearly and engagingly, making complex terms and concepts, such as sustainability certification schemes, biobased value chains, cost-benefit analysis, etc., more accessible to stakeholders across the EU.

In terms of content, the video follows a narrative approach, integrating elements that describe the project’s objectives and assets. The diversity of characters reflects the project's inclusive vision. This approach ensured that the project reached a broad audience, regardless of their familiarity with sustainability certification and biobased value chains. The video duration is limited to under 2 minutes and 30 seconds to maintain the viewer's attention. Finally, to improve accessibility for an international audience, the amount of written text has been kept to a minimum, recognising that not all viewers may be fluent in English.

Beyond the Project

The promotional video will remain accessible on the project’s YouTube channel and website, ensuring continued visibility even after the project ends. As part of the project’s long-term digital legacy, it will serve as an introductory tool for anyone seeking to learn more about sustainability certification and biobased value chains.

Figure 12. Screenshot from SUSTCERT4BIOBASED video

Figure 13. Screenshots from SUSTCERT4BIOBASED video

5.1.6 Recorded webinars (new)

To boost the project's visibility, reach more people beyond our Nol members and social media followers, and expand our outreach, **we launched a series of webinars**. We recorded (after asking

Figure 14. 1st Nol meeting

all Nol participants for their consent) and shared presentations from invited speakers at our Nol meetings on our YouTube channel [here](#). Each Nol meeting featured guest speakers covering different topics, helping us keep our research insights and Nol meeting talks accessible even after the completion of the project while also engaging a wider audience. **The thematic focus of each webinar is presented below:**

- ✓ **1st Nol meeting:** Our invited speaker gave an insightful talk on the impact of the European Parliament's Directive on the role and future of existing Voluntary Certification Schemes. Uploaded on our YouTube channel [here](#).
- ✓ **2nd Nol meeting:** The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED coordinator presented the aim of BiobasedCert and the structure of the Joint Monitoring System, currently renamed to **BIOBASED Monitoring Tool**. To deepen participants' understanding of the certification process, Control Union gave a brief talk explaining how certification works. Both presentations are uploaded on our YouTube channel [here](#) and [here](#), respectively.

Figure 15. 2nd Nol meeting

- ✓ **3rd Nol meeting:** Our Nol members gained insights into Forest biomass certification through a presentation on the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) certification scheme. Uploaded on our YouTube channel [here](#).
- ✓ **4th Nol meeting:** Our Nol members gained insights into regulations relevant for the textile sector and on the research conducted under the BIORADAR project on bio-based polymers used in the textile industry and their technical applications. Uploaded on our YouTube channel [here](#).
- ✓ **5th Nol meeting:** The fifth bi-annual SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Network of Interest meeting took place online on May 2nd, 2025, gathering participants from across the project community to discuss evolving perspectives on sustainability certifications and ecolabels.

Figure 16.3rd Nol meeting

Figure 17. 4th Nol meeting

Figure 18. 5th Nol meeting

This session brought forward views from international organisations (ISEAL and GEN) and reflected on the role of voluntary standards and ecolabels in accelerating sustainable markets. The meeting gathered 15 participants. Uploaded on our YouTube channel [here](#) and [here](#).

Uploading the webinars to our YouTube channel helped us connect with a wider range of people and keep our insights liveable even after each meeting ended. Specifically:

- The YouTube uploads made it **easy for anyone who couldn't attend live** to still access the content whenever they had time.
- Watching the videos on YouTube meant that stakeholders could go back to parts they found particularly interesting and act as a source of inspiration.
- Encouraged stakeholders to share the videos within their networks, **increasing the overall reach**.
- We created a kind of digital archive. **Stakeholders could revisit the talks whenever they wanted**, making the presentations a lasting resource. This might be especially helpful for people working on related projects or wanting to dive deeper into sustainability certification-related topics.

- **YouTube’s comment section offers stakeholders a place to ask follow-up questions** or share thoughts after the Nol meetings. This can keep the engagement alive and give room for discussions to continue.
- **The recorded webinars were easy to share and spread**, so more people in related fields or industries could learn from the presentations and get involved in future conversations.

In short, uploading the Nol presentations on YouTube helped us reach and engage with people in a much more lasting and meaningful way and create a digital space where knowledge could continue to grow and be shared long after each Nol ended.

Figure 19. Nol thematic webinars

Beyond the Project

The webinars, now archived on the project’s YouTube channel, represent a lasting resource that will continue to support knowledge sharing and engagement. Though no further live webinars are planned post-project, the recorded content will remain accessible for future audiences, ensuring that the insights generated during the project continue to reach stakeholders. The videos can be repurposed in future projects and conferences and will serve as a reference for anyone interested in sustainability certification schemes or biobased value chains.

5.1.7 Other promotional material (updated)

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED has produced additional ad-hoc material to help consortium partners in their dissemination needs.

Figure 20. Examples of other promotional material

5.2 Digital tools

Most of our audience chose to get informed through our digital communication channels. To better communicate its messages, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED focused on building a strong online presence in multiple digital platforms aiming to reach as many diverse stakeholders as possible. In particular SUSTCERT4BIOBASED created:

- (i) a website;
- (ii) a bi-annual newsletter;
- (iii) various SMAs.

5.2.1 SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website (updated)

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website was launched on M5 (October 2022) and constituted the key digital dissemination platform of the project, presenting its progress to wider audiences. The website will be accessible by the general public for 4 more years.

The website became operational in M5 (October 2022) and has since served as the online platform for disseminating news and updates. The website's structure and content have been designed for user-friendliness and to clearly convey the project's concept and objectives. Additionally, the website contains key information about the project's progress, including news and event announcements, to keep stakeholders informed. Rather than targeting a specific audience, the website works as a dynamic repository of project information and news, making it an online platform for reaching out to a broad range of stakeholders. WHITE is the partner responsible for the website's development, maintenance, and technical management, as well as overseeing web editing and content development. The website's URL is <https://sustcert4biobased.eu>, and the project's contact email aligns with it (info@sustcert4biobased.eu).

The website was developed using WordPress. Special attention was given to creating a responsive and accessible website, ensuring compatibility with various devices, including mobile ones, to prevent the exclusion of potential stakeholders. The website includes some general information

about the project and dedicated sections to present our BIOBASED cluster, its objectives and the members of the Advisory Board, all project outcomes such as public deliverables, dissemination material, and newsletters (also available for downloading) and a dedicated section for subscription to our Network of Interest. The project’s Privacy and Cookies Policy is available on the website.

Beyond the project

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website will remain accessible to the public for 4 years, continuing to provide access to project outcomes, resources, and dissemination materials. As the project reaches its conclusion, the website will serve as a lasting reference for stakeholders interested in sustainability certification, biobased value chains, and the project’s other key outcomes.

5.2.2 Website updates (new)

After the initial launch of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's website, and with the aim of enhancing its content and improving the user experience, WHITE team implemented several changes and introduced new sections. These new sections include:

- A. New visual elements on the homepage that introduce the focus areas of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, the synergies, the Network and the cluster;**

Figure 22. Updates on the website (1)

Figure 21. Website BIOBASEDCERT cluster section

B. A dedicated section to present our BIOBASEDCERT Cluster and our joint efforts to develop the BMT;

A dedicated section has been created to showcase the work carried out by the BIOBASEDCERT group, with the goal of promoting the group and its objectives. This section highlights the group's key achievement: the development of a comprehensive monitoring system. A dedicated page provides an in-depth explanation of the monitoring system, detailing its development process and offering guidance on how users can benefit from this.

Figure 23. Cluster dedicated page (1)

Figure 24. Cluster dedicated page (2)

C. Public deliverables, scientific publications, webinars, and academic materials from the project's tasks and findings (e.g., Detailed factsheets);

Figure 25. Website updates (3)

D. Additional dissemination materials highlighting SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's synergies, and updates in the related projects and initiatives sections.

Figure 26. Website updates (4)

5.2.3 Website Analytics (new)

For monitoring the website's traffic, we utilised the Google Analytics service. This tool provided valuable statistics that assisted us in optimising the website and our dissemination strategy. More specific metrics, which are monitored as part of the D&C strategy, are detailed in the next sub-sections.

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Status (M36)
Website visits	>10.000	10.665 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Overall, it appears that the website has gained interest from various groups of stakeholders around the world. This is evident from the increased number of users and visitors to the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website. The website has received around 27.000 session visits from over 2.000 website visitors worldwide, resulting in over 11.000 SUSTCERT4BIOBASED page views.

The increased visibility of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's website can be attributed to several factors, including:

- (i) The continuous website update with project and external news and events related to SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's progress, internal events, presence in external events and general updates on sustainability certification schemes and labels.
- (ii) The integration of the website with the project's SMAs by posting website articles on these platforms.
- (iii) The integration of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED NoI networking section into the project's website.
- (iv) The distribution of the website through engagement and research activities, such as including the website QR code in the project's presentations and social media posts.

The increase in the number of new users in the 3rd year can be attributed to actions such as the increased posting on all our SMAs (2-3 posts per week) alongside our sister projects by linking every post to a relevant article on the project's website and the increased reposting of posts from our consortium partners. Furthermore, the content and structure of the website were constantly updated and enriched, resulting in an overachievement of our KPI of 10.000 website visits.

5.2.4 *Newsletter (updated)*

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED committed to producing a biannual newsletter to keep stakeholders informed about the project's progress. Over the course of the project, **6 newsletters** were distributed to the target audience and uploaded to the project's website. Each newsletter provided updates on key activities and developments, offering an alternative way to engage existing subscribers. Additionally, they served as tools to attract and retain stakeholders who were less active on social media, as well as citizens who may not have engaged during the project's initial phases.

The newsletters were prepared by White Research, with project partners contributing content as needed. The Mailchimp platform was used for design, distribution, and analytics tracking.

Highlights from the Newsletters:

Newsletter	Short Information	link
#1	This edition introduced the project's objectives the kick-off meeting in Wageningen, Netherlands, the collaboration at the Projects2Projects workshop and introduced sister projects, HARMONITOR and STAR4BBS.	link
#2	Celebrating a year of progress, this edition shared updates from events like the joint engagement event at the 31st European Biomass Conference and Exhibition and the yearly progress meeting in Bologna, Italy	link
#3	Marking 1.5 years of achievements, highlighted the second NoI meeting, the co-creation event with sister projects, the project's promotional video, an article in Innovation News Network, and an interview with Network of Interest member	link
#4	This edition showcased the project's achievements and key highlights from the third NoI meeting, the event at the 32nd European Biomass Conference & Exhibition on monitoring sustainability certification schemes and labels for bio-based products, as well as participation in external events and collaborations with sister projects	link
#5	This edition highlighted the significant progress in the development of the BMT , key takeaways from the 4th NoI meeting, the project's participation in multiple events, including the workshop at the Renewable Materials Conference in Cologne, a webinar organized by the sister project 3-CO. Readers were also invited to fill in a stakeholder survey, explore recent webinars and publications, and learn about the newly introduced sister projects expanding the project's collaborative efforts	link
#6	This edition concludes the project by presenting its key events and highlighting the final event organized in Brussels by the BIOBASEDCERT cluster.	link

Figure 25. Screenshots from our Newsletter

Newsletter subscriptions complied with GDPR provisions. Subscribers were required to agree to the project's Privacy Policy and could unsubscribe at any time. A dedicated section at the bottom of the website allowed new users to subscribe. By the time of composing this deliverable (May 2025) the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED newsletter had 206 subscribers.

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current status (M34)
Newsletter subscribers	>200	206 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Beyond the project

The newsletter was sent to all subscribers upon its release, and each issue was uploaded to the project's website [here](#). Although no additional newsletters will be issued after the project's official conclusion, the newsletters produced during the project will remain accessible on the project website. These newsletters contain valuable insights, updates, and key findings from the project's activities

5.2.5 Social Media Accounts (SMAs)

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's Social Media Accounts (SMAs) proved to be valuable tools for consistently promoting the project and its activities in a visually engaging and interactive manner. The project's Facebook page, X account (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn profile, and YouTube channel were established in July 2022 (M2). Given the widespread daily use of social media by the targeted stakeholders, these platforms were leveraged extensively, serving as essential digital communication channels for expanding the project's reach and engagement. Additionally, SMAs facilitated the redirection of audiences to the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website, often by promoting existing website content. This integration played an integral role in the project's overall communication strategy, ensuring that key updates, achievements, and events reached a broader audience effectively.

The target audiences addressed by each social media channel and the specific objectives are presented in the following table:

Table 4. The target audiences addressed by each social media channel

Social Network	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Target Audience	Objectives
Facebook	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scheme/Label owners • Standardisation bodies • Certification bodies • NGOs • Industrial biobased value chain actors • Biomass producers • Industrial operators and traders • Farmers • Civil Society • Entrepreneurs • General public 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Build a network of followers ✓ Update them on the project's progress and project events ✓ Publish relevant posts
X (formerly Twitter)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scheme/Label owners • Standardisation bodies • Certification bodies • EU policymakers • Policy advisors • Governments • Local authorities • NGOs • International Organisations • Unions • Research Centres • Research groups • Individual researchers • Universities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Communicate key messages and the project's outcomes ✓ Announce projects and upcoming events ✓ Retweet relevant content from other Horizon Europe and other relevant projects
LinkedIn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU policy makers • Policy advisors • Research Centres • Research groups • Individual researchers • Universities • International organisations • NGOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Present the project and boost professional and expert discussions ✓ Involve NoI
YouTube	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scheme/Label owners • Standardisation bodies • Certification bodies • Industrial biobased value chain actors • Biomass producers • Industrial • Operators and traders • Farmers • Civil Society • Entrepreneurs • General public • Civil society organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Upload promotional video ✓ Contribute to increasing the visibility of the project

WHITE was responsible for the management of SUSTCERT4BIOASED's SMAs, while all partners contributed to:

- Becoming a follower (like or follow the page/profile);
- Promoting the accounts in their networks;
- Suggesting relevant profiles that SUSTCERT4BIOBASED should connect with;
- Sharing interesting articles and news;
- Promoting posts and news through the SMAs of their own organisations.

Key takeaway from the project's dissemination efforts:

Circulating significant posts within the consortium ensured that key updates and achievements were shared across a wide network, increasing the project's visibility. By asking consortium members to repost our social media content, we were able to leverage their networks to reach a broader and more diverse audience. This collective effort strengthened the project's online presence and enhanced engagement with stakeholders.

Facebook

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's Facebook page was established in M2. This channel offered a valuable opportunity to share SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's news and results with followers interested in related topics. More specifically, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's Facebook account served as a:

- A news and discussion hub where information related to the project and topics of bioeconomy and circular economy was shared;
- A platform to deliver updates on the developments and results of the project (e.g., published reports, scientific publications, key events, activities, and important achievements);
- A link to other similar groups and pages associated with relevant topics.

Figure 26. Screenshot of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED'S Facebook page

To monitor the performance of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED page, Facebook Analytics were used.

Figure 27. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's Facebook page analytics

A key takeaway from the project’s dissemination efforts:

Overall, the use of Facebook proved beneficial for sharing news with followers. Since July 2022, 120 posts have been uploaded to the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED page. The social media strategy was successful, resulting in 50 followers and enabling the project to communicate effectively within the Facebook community. The effectiveness of the account was evident in the Total reach (1,463 views), which indicated the number of people who had seen any posts within their news feeds, on the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED page, or shared by their networks. This metric also included individuals who did not follow the project on Facebook. In terms of the sustainability of our Facebook account, we plan to keep the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED page open for the next few years.

X (formerly Twitter)

Similar to Facebook, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED X account was launched in July 2022 (M2). Twitter (before transitioning to X) proved to be an essential dissemination tool for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, as it kept the project partners, who were very active on the platform, engaged and enabled all followers to stay updated on project news and outcomes from relevant initiatives. X was particularly valuable during events where information needed to be immediately shared such as during our two engagement events within the framework of EUBCE. The platform also helped establish new synergies with similar initiatives as we kept on following multiple related projects that were appearing in our feed. The use of hashtags allowed the project’s messages to reach broader audiences, and the concise text in posts actively engaged a wide range of stakeholders.

In this context, the X account acted as a:

- General dissemination platform, sharing key messages of the project and directing users to other project-related platforms/tools (e.g., SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's website, newsletter promotional video) while providing updates on the project’s development (upcoming events, participation in external events, project results, etc.);

- Newsfeed platform, collecting and updating news from other relevant projects and organisations;
- Community of followers interested in the topic and sector.

Even though not all SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners had an X account, the ones who had contributed to the X account regularly by retweeting content via their personal accounts.

Figure 28. Screenshot of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED'S X account

Twitter analytics were used to monitor the account's performance. Due to the transition to X, analytics are no longer available in the free version of the platform. This change has impacted our ability to track detailed engagement metrics for the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED account. As a result, we no longer have access to the same level of performance insights we previously had on Twitter.

A key takeaway from the project's dissemination efforts:

Since July 2022, 120 posts have been uploaded to the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED account. Although X was not the most popular social media platform among our consortium for the project, our strategy proved successful, as we gained more than 100 followers from other EU projects and initiatives. Appearing in the 'Who to Follow' section on X provided significant visibility for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, allowing the project to be associated with similar initiatives and attract a wider, relevant audience. This placement helped increase engagement by connecting the project with stakeholders and organisations interested in sustainability certification topics. It also fostered networking opportunities, enhancing collaboration and knowledge-sharing with other projects in the same sector. In terms of the sustainability of this account, we plan to keep the account open for people to be able to check all the uploaded posts.

LinkedIn

The LinkedIn platform was selected to promote the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project to a more professional audience. The project's profile was created in M2 to present the project and provide updates on its progress. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners strongly supported the project's LinkedIn profile and invited followers while reposting the project's posts. The project took a more institutional approach on LinkedIn to foster professional and expert discussions on topics of common interest, involving the Network of Interest as well. The metrics and insights provided by LinkedIn were used to assess the project's performance.

Figure 29. Screenshot of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED'S LinkedIn account

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project played also a key role in the establishment of the **Joint Group on Certification and Labelling Schemes for the EU Bioeconomy**. This group was created to bring together stakeholders from various sectors within the bioeconomy to discuss and collaborate on the development and implementation of certification and labelling schemes that promote sustainability. The group aimed to foster knowledge sharing, align efforts across initiatives, and contribute to the harmonisation of standards within the EU bioeconomy, ultimately supporting the transition towards more sustainable and transparent bio-based products.

Figure 30. Joint LinkedIn group Certification and Labelling Schemes for the EU Bioeconomy

Given the professional nature of this social network, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's LinkedIn page is more project-focused, hosting content that is either directly related to the project (e.g., the project's latest news, progress, upcoming events) or content that involves broader developments within our BIOBASEDCERT cluster expected to have a direct impact on the project (e.g., important news from the sector, relevant EC initiatives). The metrics provided by LinkedIn are being utilised to monitor and assess the project's performance on this platform.

Figure 31. Posts on our social media

Overall, as of the time of composing this deliverable, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED has engaged 488 followers on LinkedIn. Through the use of LinkedIn, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED has the opportunity to stay engaged with the latest developments and participate in professional and expert discussions on issues of common interest within a wide range of professional networks. Additionally, LinkedIn has contributed significantly to introducing the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED promotional video to a wider audience by engaging more than 1000 stakeholders on their feed. The sustainability of dissemination of results is significantly enhanced by the Joint LinkedIn Group for the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project. Co-developing this group allows the project to continue reaching and engaging a professional audience even after its completion. The group can serve as a platform for sharing key updates, research findings, and best practices while fostering ongoing discussions on sustainability certification-related topics. It can also promote events organised by the projects which participate in the group, ensuring that stakeholders remain informed about upcoming activities and developments. This collective group helps maintain the project's visibility, encourages knowledge-sharing among stakeholders, and supports the long-term impact of our dissemination efforts within the community.

YouTube channel

YouTube was chosen as the primary digital channel for communicating the identity and goals of the project in a visual way. A YouTube channel for **SUSTCERT4BIOBASED** was created in July 2022 (M2) to upload the project’s promotional video and other project-related videos in one easily accessible location, to enhance visibility and engage the audience.

Figure 32. YouTube channel screenshot

As an additional stakeholder engagement boost, we uploaded nine more videos, including the below:

- 1 video to present our BIOBASEDCERT cluster;
- 8 videos that include recorded presentations from our online Nol speakers.

Figure 33. Recorded NOL presentations on our YouTube channel

By hosting recorded videos from our NOL on the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED YouTube channel, we have created a legacy of knowledge that will continue to benefit stakeholders beyond the project’s duration. These videos serve as a long-term resource, ensuring that expert discussions, key insights, and best practices in sustainability certification remain accessible to policymakers, researchers, industry professionals, and other relevant audiences. This initiative not only extends the project’s impact but also fosters continuous learning, collaboration, and innovation in the bioeconomy sector. By maintaining an open-access

repository of valuable content, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED strengthens its role as a reference point for future initiatives and stakeholders seeking guidance on sustainability certification.

Table 5. Overview of followers on social media KPI

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current status (M34)
Followers on social media	>1,000	1,078 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

5.3 Public Deliverables (new)

Another update in terms of digital dissemination was the creation of a new section on the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website dedicated to hosting all of the project's public deliverables. After consulting with the Project Officer (PO) and accepting the public deliverables, permission was granted to the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED team to publicly upload and distribute these deliverables. The dissemination of these deliverables aimed to enhance the visibility of the project's scientific results, with a primary focus on academic and policy-oriented audiences. Additionally, sharing these materials through social media allowed a broader audience to better understand the key concepts and objectives of each deliverable. All deliverables are available for downloading and uploaded to our online community in Zenodo. How do our actions enhance the sustainability of our dissemination efforts? Making all SUSTCERT4BIOBASED deliverables available for download and uploading them to our online community in Zenodo ([here](#)) enhances the sustainability of dissemination in several ways:

- ✓ **Long-term Accessibility** – Zenodo provides a permanent repository, ensuring that all project deliverables remain accessible to researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders even after the project ends.
- ✓ **Wider Reach & Open Access** – By making deliverables freely available, the project extends its impact beyond its immediate network, allowing global audiences to access and utilise its findings.
- ✓ **Scientific Credibility & Citation** – Zenodo assigns DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) to uploaded materials, enabling proper citation and increasing their visibility in academic and professional communities.
- ✓ **Community Engagement & Knowledge Sharing** – Hosting deliverables in an online community encourages collaboration and interaction, fostering continued discussions and knowledge exchange among experts in sustainability certification and the bio-based sector.
- ✓ **Integration with Other Open Science Initiatives** – Zenodo links with OpenAIRE and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), ensuring that project results contribute to broader European research and innovation efforts.

By leveraging **Zenodo**, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED ensures that its results remain impactful, reusable, and accessible, supporting ongoing research, policymaking, and industry advancements in sustainability certification.

Figure 34. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's public deliverables uploaded to the website

Figure 34. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Zenodo account

5.4 Events (updated)

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED has participated in and organised several events to promote its outcomes and expand its influence on the implementation of sustainability certification schemes in the biobased sector. These events have provided valuable opportunities to engage with stakeholders, showcase the project's results, and foster discussions on how to streamline sustainability certification in biobased products. By participating in such events, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED has effectively raised awareness, built new collaborations, and contributed to the ongoing development of best practices and policies in sustainability certification.

5.4.1 Project's events

The events organised within the framework of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED were designed to raise awareness about the project's concept, promote its results, and engage key stakeholders to support its activities. These events also aimed to gather valuable feedback on the outcomes produced throughout the project.

To ensure wide participation, the project leveraged its partners' extended networks, social media followers, and key assets such as the Nol to attract a diverse range of participants. These efforts ensured that the events reached the right audiences and encouraged active involvement.

A significant highlight of the event series was the organisation of **21 project events**, each playing a critical role in facilitating the project's development and contributing to its overall progress. These events were carefully planned to provide participants with in-depth insights into various aspects of the project and serve as collaborative spaces for discussion and feedback.

In total, the events contributed greatly to the success of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, not only by promoting its outcomes but also by ensuring continuous collaboration and feedback from its stakeholders.

Over the project's lifetime and after we formed the synergy with our sister projects HARMONITOR and STAR4BBS, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED tailored its initial plans and organised the following events.

Table 6. List with our project events

No	Event's title	Type of event	Date
1	Sustainability Certification of Biobased Products Parallel event at EUBCE 2023 – 31st European Biomass Conference & Exhibition	1 st Engagement event	June 2023
2	Monitoring sustainability certification schemes and labels for bio-based products Parallel event at EUBCE 2024 – 32nd European Biomass Conference & Exhibition	2 nd Engagement event	June 2024
3	How can voluntary certification systems support the transition to a sustainable circular bioeconomy Engagement Event at Brussels 2025 (Final event)	3 rd engagement events	May 2025
4	1 st Network of Interest meeting The Green Claim Regulation and the significance of voluntary certification schemes	Nol Meeting	June 2023
5	2 nd Network of Interest meeting The certification process and how it works	Nol Meeting	April 2024
6	3 rd Network of Interest Meeting Sustainable Forestry and Certification	Nol Meeting	May 2024
7	4 th Network of Interest meeting Sustainable Textiles: The Bio-based shift	Nol Meeting	December 2024

8	5th Network of Interest meeting The future of sustainability certifications, views from international organisations	NoI Meeting	May 2025
9	Workshop with Joint Advisory Board members	Workshop	February 2023
10	Robust and Effective Sustainability Certification for Bio-based Systems - BIOBASEDCERT cluster online co-creation workshop	Workshop	December 2023
11	Workshop on the first results of the pilot testing of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT)	Workshop	May 2024
12	The Role of Certification in Global Trade Flows in Bio-based Value Chains	Workshop	June 2024
13	1st BIOBASEDCERT Roundtable Meeting	Workshop	July 2024
14	2nd BIOBASEDCERT Roundtable Meeting	Workshop	September 2024
15	Driving Sustainability through Certification: Unveiling the Costs and Benefits of Certification Schemes in Bio-Based Industries and Products	Workshop	November 2024
16	3rd BIOBASEDCERT Roundtable Meeting & BMT workshop with policy makers	Workshop	December 2024
17	Workshop on the second testing phase of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT)	Workshop	January 2025
18	Spanish Regional Workshop on the use of municipal solid waste (MSW) as an abundant source for the manufacture of circular products.	Workshop	February 2025
19	4th BIOBASEDCERT Roundtable Meeting	Workshop	April 2025
20	Dutch regional workshop: Sustainability Certification in the Dutch Bio-economy: an Exploration	Workshop	April 2025
21	5th BIOBASEDCERT Roundtable Meeting	Workshop	May 2025

The organised SUSTCERT4BIOBASED events offered several key benefits, both for the project itself and its participants. These benefits include:

- ✓ **Knowledge Sharing and Capacity Building**

The workshops provided a platform for stakeholders to exchange knowledge, ideas, and best practices. Participants gained insights into the project's progress, technical advancements, and how they could contribute to its success.

✓ **Stakeholder Engagement**

By bringing together diverse stakeholders, including researchers, industry representatives, and policymakers, the workshops increased inter-project collaboration and strengthened partnerships. This engagement was crucial for gathering feedback and aligning the project with the needs of its stakeholders.

✓ **Facilitating Project Development**

The workshops played an essential role in advancing the project's goals. By discussing key challenges, solutions, and opportunities, the workshops helped refine the project's direction and identify areas for improvement.

✓ **Raising Awareness**

The events helped increase awareness of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project, its objectives, and its potential impact. This not only supported the project's visibility but also attracted new participants and partners who could contribute to its success.

✓ **Feedback and Validation**

The workshops provided a direct channel for stakeholders to give feedback on the project's outcomes and deliverables. This feedback was vital for ensuring that the project met the needs of its target audiences and improved its final outputs.

✓ **Networking Opportunities**

Participants had the opportunity to network with other experts, professionals, and organisations in the field, potentially leading to new collaborations, partnerships, or business opportunities.

✓ **Promoting Sustainable Practices**

By focusing on the development of sustainable biobased solutions, the workshops contributed to promoting sustainable practices and innovation within the sector, aligning with the overall mission of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project.

These events played a pivotal role in advancing the project's objectives, ensuring its alignment with stakeholder needs and expectations. The events of most workshops have been shared in dedicated articles on our website [here](#), which serve as valuable resources. These articles can act as a roadmap for stakeholders interested in organising similar events, providing insights and guidance based on the lessons learned and best practices from the workshops.

Figure 35. Photos of our project events (1)

Figure 36. Photos of our project events (2)

5.4.2 External events and conferences

Throughout our project’s duration, we had the chance to participate in multiple external events and conferences and as mentioned in D6.1, where we set our goals in terms of participating in external events and conferences, we managed actively to:

- Present the project (concept, approach, etc.).
- Promote the project’s results.
- Promote SUSTCERT4BIOBASED actions and events.
- Establish synergies and contacts with relevant projects and initiatives.
- Engage relevant stakeholders in the project’s activities (e.g. NoI, etc.).
- Promote the project’s dissemination channels (website, SMAs, etc.).
- Stay up to date on the latest technological and research findings.

Engaging in external events and conferences provided the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED team with the opportunity to disseminate knowledge, shape policy developments, and enhance stakeholder participation in the bio-based sector. These events enabled us to foster strategic networking, form synergies, and exchange best practices and research ideas.

The first version of the DCP presented an indicative list of identified conferences and events. This final DCP version offers a list of external events where SUSTCERT4BIOBASED was present.

The partners who participated in external events followed the visual identity of the project and used the official promotional materials (leaflet, poster, .ppt template, etc.). Finally, after the event, partners completed the reporting template (Annex II), which can be found in the project’s online repository.

Table 7. External events where SUSTCERT4BIOBASED participated based on partners reporting

Event's title	Date	Role	Links
Projects2Projects Mobilisation and Mutual learning workshop - satellite event of the High-Level EU Conference “Bioeconomy – Enabling the European Green Deal in Challenging Times, Brussels	5 October 2022	Presentation, Physical participation	link
Connected Circularity Day at WUR	22 November 2022	Physical participation	link
Environmental and circularity assessment of biobased products, Workshop organised for the working group on sustainability of biological resources with representatives of various Dutch Ministries	13 December 2022	Presentation, Physical Participation	N/A
SUSTRACK and EuBioNet Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshop among projects in standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring	14 February 2023	Online participation (providing feedback, networking)	link
World Circular Economy Forum 2024	15 April 2024	Physical Participation & Information Booth	link
Six pathways to smart certification of bio-based systems	7 June 2024 (online only)	Presentation and online participation	link
EUBCE 2024	26 June 2024 (physical)	Two oral, one poster presentation related to results from the project, Physical participation	link

Event's title	Date	Role	Links
It's Like traditional plastic, but made from plants	27 November 2024 (online only)	Online presentation	link
Navigating the CSR Directive: Leveraging Voluntary Sustainability Standards and Research to Strengthen Bio-Based Industry Reporting	14 March 2025 (online only)	Online presentation	link
Digital Solutions for a Bio-Based Future – Empowering Industry and Consumers (3CO/BioReCer webinar on digital tools)	8 April 2025 (online only)	Support/involved project, Online presentation	link
Navigating the new EU legislations to address greenwashing: how standards and research projects can support the bio-based industry	25 March 2025 (online)	Support organisation, Online presentation	link
Projects4Future: Shaping tomorrow: Horizon Europe projects' contributing to boost the transition towards a circular bio-based economy (SUSTRACK Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshop)	6 May 2025 (online only)	Online Participation, Providing input from the project in deriving recommendations	link
1st STAR4BBS Co-Creation Workshop	26 January 2023	Online participation (providing feedback)	link
2nd STAR4BBS co-creation workshop	26 May 2023 (Online)	Online Participation (providing feedback)	link
SUSTRACK focus group workshop – “Limits, barriers and solutions to boost the transition towards a circular bio-based economy”	9 June 2023 (online)	Online Participation (providing feedback)	link
Side event organised by Aligned and Calimero projects as part of the Life Cycle Management conference	July 2023	Physical Participation (providing feedback)	link

Event's title	Date	Role	Links
ALIGNED LCA Methodology Workshop	17 October 2023 (online only)	Online Participation (providing feedback)	link
SUSTRACK Inspire Conference	16 November 2023	Online Participation (providing feedback)	link
Workshop organised by RVO (in English: Dutch Enterprise Agency, a Dutch policy advisory body), which is currently developing a regulatory sustainability framework for the use of biological materials/ biobased products.	February 2024	Physical Participation, Providing input and feedback	N/A
2nd ALIGNED LCA Methodology Workshop	3 May 2024 (online only)	Online Participation (providing feedback)	link
EU CRCF Carbon storage certification of buildings workshop	24 September 2024 (online only)	Online Participation	link
ROBIN 1st Mutual Learning Workshop	14 October 2024	Physical participation (participant)	link
EU Bioeconomy Conference	October 2022	Participation	link
Plastic Waste Free World Conference & Expo	13-14 November 2022	Participation	link
CEN TC 411 Meeting	March 2025	Participation, online presentation	N/A
II Annual Multi-stakeholder meeting of BioReCer	27 November 2024 (Online only)	Online Participation (providing feedback)	link
European Rural Circular Bioeconomy Conference	13 May 2025	Participation	N/A

Figure 37. Participation in external events (1)

To ensure strategic outreach, the sustainability of our dissemination results, and increased visibility and impact, the table below provides indicative events and conferences where the team can present its findings and results after the project's completion.

Table 8. Indicative list with external events and conferences for presenting SUSTCERT4BIOBASED findings

Conference	Link
European Biomass Conference and Exhibition	link
European Bioplastics	link
EURAS Annual Standardisation Conference	link
World Bioeconomy Forum	link
EU Green Week	link
European Forum for Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy	link
International Bioeconomy Conference - The European Summit	link
Renewable Materials Conference	link
Sustainable Alternative and Bio-based Materials	link
International Consortium on Applied Bioeconomy Research	link

Dissemination KPI	Target (M36)	Current status (M36)
Participation in external events	>10	27 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

During the duration of the project, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners participated in 27 external events, both virtually and physically. This metric surpasses the final target of 10 events. In these events, partners played pivotal roles, such as participants, discussants or presenters, maximising the project's visibility. It is evident that participation in external events has proven to be an effective mean of disseminating SUSTCERT4BIOBASED to both the EU community and policymakers, while also establishing a robust audience. Even after the project concludes, the project partners plan to leverage its outcomes and showcase the key achievements at national and international events. Post-project activities are already being planned, including presenting the results at the upcoming EUBCE event in 2025.

5.5 Publications

5.5.1 Scientific publications

As mentioned in the initial version of the DCP, scientific publications are important channels for presenting SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's outcomes to academic, research, policy and industrial target audiences. Thus, creating knowledge impact and giving the incentive to other researchers and stakeholders to use the project's results in their own work contributes to disseminating the project further.

Although we did not have a KPI related to scientific publications, our consortium coordinated efforts and worked towards scientific publications. This research legacy can help other EU projects and initiatives to:

- To get inspired and continue the project's scientific work;
- Act as a source of knowledge and capitalise on our findings that can help other researchers complete/enhance their research work;
- Support the long-term sustainability of the project's impact.

Following the principles of Horizon Europe for Open Access, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED has a dedicated section on the website which presents the project's scientific publications (available for downloading [here](#))

The project team has made significant contributions to the scientific community through the following:

- **Two published scientific papers:**
 - ***Assessment of EU Bio-Based Economy Sectors Based on Environmental, Socioeconomic, and Technical Indicators***, published in *Sustainability Journal*. Víctor Fernández Ocamica, Monique Bernardes Figueirêdo, Sebastián Zapata and Carmen Bartolomé
 - ***Trade-offs and Synergies of Key Biobased Value Chains and Sustainability***, published in *Sustainability Journal*. Victor Fernandez Ocamica, Bárbara Palacino, Carmen Bartolomé, Monique Bernardes Figueirêdo, Cristina Lázaro Garcia.
- **A number of abstracts (4)** have also been submitted within the framework of the **EUBCE**.

- **Abstract (1) | EUBCE 2024:** *A system to assess and monitor the sustainability performance of existing sustainability certification schemes for biobased systems.* **Authors:** Iris Vural Gursel, Heleen Ballemans, Laura Väyrynen, Marxine Waite and Mathilde Crepy.
- **Abstract (2) | EUBCE 2024:** *Unveiling the True Value: Exploring Costs and Benefits of Sustainable Certification Schemes in the Biopolyethylene Value Chain.* **Authors:** Lusine Aramyan, Luuk Vissers, Behrang Manouchehrabadi, Karolina Niemenoja, Loek Verwijst.
- **Abstract (3) | EUBCE 2024:** *Methodology for the Socio-environmental and Socio-economic Analysis of the EU Bio-based Industry* **Authors:** Víctor Fernández Ocamica, Sebastián Zapata, Monique Bernardes Figueirêdo, Carmen Bartolomé.
- **Abstract (4) | EUBCE 2025:** *Towards Comprehensive Cost-Benefit Analysis: Incorporating Externalities in Sustainability Certification for Biobased Products.* **Authors:** Lusine Aramyan, Luuk Vissers, Scarlett Wang, Karolina Niemenoja, Loek Verwijst.
- **Abstract (5) | EUBCE 2025:** *BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring System Content level for the assessment of the sustainability certification schemes for biobased systems.* **Authors:** Iris Vural Gursel, Heleen Ballemans, Laura Väyrynen.

These efforts reflect the team's commitment to advancing knowledge in the field of sustainability certification of biobased products.

Since the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium is committed to supporting open access to scientific publications, all necessary steps have been taken to ensure free access to peer-reviewed articles resulting from the project. In alignment with the Open Data Strategy of the European Commission and following the FAIR principles, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's research outputs are made publicly accessible in a digital and online format, free of charge. Wageningen Research has national Open Access agreements with all major publishers. Therefore:

- i. All public research deliverables were published on the project's website [here](#).
- ii. Scientific publications were included in the project's website and were open access through Zenodo [here](#).

5.5.2 **Non-scientific publications**

As mentioned in the initial version of the DCP, throughout the duration of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project, partners would be invited to produce press and media releases, articles in mass media. The aim of all these efforts is to increase the project's visibility and publicity and the potential to reach out to stakeholders outside of the consortium.

To increase our project's visibility SUSTCERT4BIOBASED has published a 3-page article (led by WR and supported with feedback by the consortium partners) informing the audience about the project and its aim to the [Innovations Platform](#), a FREE publication full of exciting developments and informative articles from the technology, science and politics sectors with the issue's topic being the sustainability of biobased products. The article was available online on the 15th November 2023 and appeared in the Innovation Platform - Issue 16 published on 4th December 2023.

A second 3-page article summarising the project’s outcomes and findings will be published in the [Innovations Platform](#) - Issue 22 in June 2025. The online version of the article is already available online and can be reached [here](#).

Figure 38. The Innovation Platform magazine

Figure 39. Introductory three-page article published in Innovation Platform Magazine - Issue 16

Figure 40. The second three-page article that will be published in Innovation Platform Magazine – Issue 22

The non-scientific publications increased the project’s visibility and expanded its outreach to a wider audience. It is important to continue disseminating the project’s results beyond the scientific community, as they are relevant to a broad range of stakeholders interested in further exploring the field of sustainability certification.

In light of further disseminating the project’s presence to a wider audience, an interview with our coordinator Iris Vural Gursel was published on the Wageningen University & Research website and was part of the WFBR Circular & Biobased Economy newsletter, where she explained the development process of the BMT. The interview is available [here](#).

Figure 41. Article in WFBR Circular & Biobased Economy newsletter

CORDIS will publish an article on the results of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project in the upcoming "Innovative Bioeconomy Solutions" Results Pack, following a request from the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD).

Additionally, as part of the project’s communication activities, **press releases** have been published to keep our audience informed about its progress.

6. Roles and responsibilities (updated)

In the initial version of the DCP clearly stated that *“The allocation of responsibilities answers the question of who is going to implement the DCP. To achieve the defined objectives, the implementation of the dissemination and communication strategy will be a collective effort from all consortium partners.”*

Indeed, the dissemination activities throughout the project were a collective effort involving all partners. WHITE, as the dissemination and communication manager, monitored the activities implemented and the progress toward achieving the DCP objectives. All project partners collaborated efficiently by reposting content when requested, providing material for the project's newsletter, and organising events for offline activities. As Dissemination Managers, we also offered ad-hoc dissemination support, such as posting on our SMAs, adding events to the [EuBioNet page](#), and more, whenever needed. On the same note, we can confirm that our goals set in D6.1 were achieved and consortium partners indeed supported in terms of:

Online dissemination activities:

- Provided content for the website, SMAs and the newsletter (The contribution could be a suggestion for a Facebook or LinkedIn post, an article regarding the project or a relevant topic of the sector, or an interview);
- Promoted the website, SMAs and the newsletter through their network;
- Informed the dissemination manager about relevant events or news of the sector that could be used for content creation.

Offline activities:

- Organised events and raised awareness about the project;
- Disseminated the promotional material of the project (leaflet, poster, etc.);
- All partners through their participation in external events and conferences and through publications for online/offline sources (websites, newspapers, magazines, etc.) ensured the widest exposure and dissemination of the project.

Activities reporting:

All partners reported the carried-out dissemination and communication activities to the dissemination manager. More information about the process will follow in the respective chapter.

Beyond the project:

As the project enters its final phase, the roles of the consortium partners will evolve to ensure the sustainability of the project's results and its continued dissemination. The partners' collective effort will remain essential in maintaining and expanding the project's impact after the official conclusion.

-WHITE (Dissemination Manager): WHITE will continue to oversee the coordination of dissemination activities, ensuring that the project's results are widely shared. This includes monitoring the long-term impact of the dissemination efforts, ensuring that all public deliverables and results are properly uploaded to digital platforms, and maintaining the project's website for 4 years to support ongoing dissemination activities.

-Project partners (All):

A. Every partner will play an ongoing role in disseminating project outcomes through their networks. This involves sharing insights, reports, and materials at relevant national and international events and conferences, as well as through their social media channels and other platforms.

B. Partners will remain actively involved in promoting the project's results at key events such as the EUBCE 2025, ensuring the visibility of the project in the bioeconomy sector and contributing to discussions on sustainability certifications and standards

C. Partners will continue to engage with the broader bioeconomy community through the LinkedIn group on Certification and Labelling Schemes for the EU Bioeconomy, where they will share content, updates, and relevant news. This will facilitate the exchange of knowledge and keep the project's outcomes alive within professional networks.

7. Networks and synergies (updated)

As mentioned in D6.1, the establishment of synergies and the use of networks for the dissemination of the project's results is pivotal for its successful implementation. Throughout the past 36 months, we noticed that synergies and collective effort are crucial not only for the dissemination of the project's activities but also for the exchange of new knowledge and the sharing of ideas. This need was identified from the proposal stage and therefore a dedicated task (T6.3) that aimed to search for alignment with opportunities with relevant projects was drafted. During the operationalisation of the Task, we formed multiple synergies while creating with the other two projects funded under the same call the BIOBASEDCERT cluster.

As also mentioned in the initial version of the DCP, over the course of the project the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners:

1. Cooperated with the projects which are funded under the same call (HARMONITOR, STAR4BBS) with whom we formed the BIOBASEDCERT cluster.
2. Established synergies with projects that are relevant to the topic of sustainability certification and bioeconomy in general.

The cooperation took various forms. Indicatively:

- Mutual dissemination of events in our social media accounts and website;
- Mutual reference of projects on respective websites;
- Organisation of joint activities (e.g., workshops, dissemination events etc.);
- Participation in the Nol;
- Participation in the project's events;
- Exchange of news, experiences;
- Co-participate in conferences;
- Co-write press releases, articles etc.

Multiple potential joint activities were identified throughout the whole duration of the project and are reported below.

7.1 BIOBASEDCERT cluster (new)

Synergies with the sister projects [HARMONITOR](#) and [STAR4BBS](#) which were funded under the same call **HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01** have been established. The three projects

have formed a project cluster named **BiobasedCert** (more info available on our website [here](#)). The cooperation activities included:

- **Joint Advisory Board** (JAB) was set up and became operational.
- **BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool** (initially named Joint Monitoring System) proposal was prepared in collaboration with the sister projects and was accepted by the EC. The three projects work collaboratively on its development. A few details below:
 - The various levels of the BMT (content, system, and outcome) were developed through a collaborative effort with the sister projects. While SUSTCERT4BIOBASED led the development of the content level, it also contributed to the creation of the system and outcome levels. The decision to collaborate with the sister projects was driven by the goal of establishing a unified, comprehensive system and ensuring the continued use of the BMT beyond the duration of the three projects. The sister projects aimed to leverage each other's knowledge and expertise, subjecting the BMT to more rigorous scrutiny and optimising resource utilisation. Through this joint effort, stakeholder consultations were streamlined, reducing fatigue and avoiding duplication of work and potential confusion from developing three separate monitoring systems.
- **Collaboration in identified key thematic areas** with dedicated inter-project teams: Trade flow analysis; BMT development and testing; Costs and benefits analysis; Communication and dissemination of results. The table below showcases the cluster's efforts for joint stakeholder engagement.

Table 9. BIOBASEDCERT cluster's joint efforts in stakeholder engagement

Title	Format	Date
Kick-off meeting Advisory Board ZP-01-07 Cluster projects - Biobased value chain selection	Online	February 2023
Robust and Effective Sustainability Certification for Bio-based Systems - BIOBASEDCERT cluster online co-creation event	Online	November 2023
Workshop on the first results of the pilot testing of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT)	Online	May 2024
Workshop on the global trade flows of bio-based value chains and the role of certification - Parallel event at Renewable Materials Conference	Physical, Koln, Germany	June 2024
1st BIOBASEDCERT Roundtable Meeting	Online	July 2024
2nd BIOBASEDCERT Roundtable Meeting	Online	September 2024
Driving Sustainability through certification: Unveiling the Costs and Benefits of Certification Schemes in Bio-Based Industries and Products	Online	November 2024

3rd BIOBASEDCERT Roundtable Meeting, BMT workshop with policy makers	Physical, Brussels, Belgium	December 2024
Workshop on the second testing phase of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT)	Online	January 2025
4th BIOBASEDCERT Roundtable Meeting	Online	April 2025
5th BIOBASEDCERT Roundtable Meeting	Online	May 2025

List with joint dissemination actions within the BIOBASEDCERT cluster

- **Two joint stakeholder events** were organised as part of the **European Biomass Conference & Exhibition (EUBCE) parallel events** and **one final event** took place in Brussels (May 2025)
 - **1. Sustainability certification of bio-based products | June 2023 - Bologna, Italy.**
 - **2. Enhancing Sustainability Certification Schemes and Labels for Bio-based Systems | June 2024 - Marseille, France**
 - **3. How can voluntary certification systems support the transition to a sustainable circular bioeconomy | May 2025 – Bussels, Belgium**

Figure 42. Clusters' engagement events

- **Five (5) joint deliverables were submitted:**
 - Mid-term policy brief of the BiobasedCert Project Cluster
 - Mid-term Clustering Report for HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07
 - Final policy brief of the BiobasedCert Project Cluster
 - Final Clustering Report for HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07
 - BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool
- **Application and participation in the Horizon Results Booster Module A, Module B and Module C – common identity created, templates, cluster’s promotional video within the service.**

Figure 44. Cluster's promotional material created throughout the duration of the HRB services we followed

Figure 43. Module A & Module C HRB reports

- **Co-Ownership Agreement for BIOBASEDCERT cluster assets.**

7.2 Our other synergies (new)

As stated in the initial version of this Deliverable, several potential networks and relevant projects were identified from the early stages of the project to foster synergies. At the initial stages of the project, WHITE compiled an initial list, which was continuously updated throughout the project's duration to identify new opportunities for collaboration.

Throughout the project's duration, we established numerous synergies with other initiatives, strengthening our outreach and advancing our vision and objectives. These collaborations were maintained at the dissemination level, ensuring continuous engagement and mutual promotion. Specifically, we:

Standard actions we implemented with all our sister projects.

- ✓ Included all synergy projects in the dedicated **synergies** section of our website (more info available [here](#)).
- ✓ Shared content related to our collaborations across our communication channels. Common posts were made from our sister projects.
- ✓ Encouraged them to become active members of our **NoI**. Invited synergy partners to participate in our **NoI meetings**.
- ✓ Published dedicated articles to introduce and highlight these synergies to our audience.
- ✓ Promoted our synergies through our Newsletter.
- ✓ Co-organised or participated in events;
 - Bioradar presenting at the 4th NoI meeting about their results related to the textile industry;
 - Redol project and SUSTCERT4BIOBASED co-organising workshop with regional stakeholders in Spain;
 - Supported STAR4BBS in webinar on March 25th, 2025 (Navigating the new EU legislations to address greenwashing: how standards and research projects can support the bio-based industry);
 - Supported the event Digital Solutions for a Bio-Based Future – Empowering Industry and Consumers (3CO/BioReCer webinar on digital tools);
 - Establishment of a joint LinkedIn group [Certification and Labelling Schemes for the EU BioEconomy](#);
 - Participate in sister projects' events and workshops as participants, providing feedback.

Table 10 below presents the updated and final list of our synergies.

Table 10. Final list with our synergy projects and initiatives

Sister Projects	Title	Description	Website
HARMONITOR	Harmonisation and monitoring platform for CSLs to advance the sustainability of bio-based systems	Funded under the same call. The project aims to improve the effectiveness of CSLs in different sectors of the EU Bioeconomy.	link
STAR4BBS	Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems	Funded under the same call. The project aims to maximize the potential of sustainability CSLs to support a successful transition to sustainable bio-based economy.	link
WaysTUP!	Value chains for disruptive transformation of urban biowaste into biobased products in the city context	The project aims to demonstrate the establishment of new value chains for urban biowaste utilisation through a multi-stakeholder approach.	link
SUSTRACK	Supporting the identification of policy priorities and recommendations for designing a sustainable track towards circular bio-based systems.	The project aims to identify environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy and improve existing assessment methodologies as well as develop guidelines and policy recommendations according to scenarios analysed in the project.	link
ROBIN	Deploying circular bioeconomies at regional level with a territorial approach.	ROBIN aims to empower Europe's regions to adapt their governance models and structures in ways that accelerate the achievement of their circular bioeconomy targets while promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts.	link
MAINSTREAMBIO	Mainstreaming small-scale bio-based solutions across rural Europe via regional Multi-actor Innovation Platforms and tailored innovation support	MainstreamBIO sets out to get small-scale bio-based solutions into mainstream practice across 7 EU rural regions (NL, PL, DK, SE, BG, ES, IE), by establishing regional Multi-actor Innovation Platforms (MIPs) each with a variety of feedstocks, infrastructure, and expertise, in the aim of co-creating sustainable business model pathways in line with regional potentials and policy initiatives.	link
3-CO	Concise Consumer Communication through	The aim of the 3-CO project is to develop and demonstrate viability of a supportive framework for Label and Certification Schemes (LCS) on Business-to-	link

Sister Projects	Title	Description	Website
	Robust Labels for Bio-based Systems	Consumers (B to C) communication for industrial bio-based products that enables and supports consumers to make more sustainable buying choices.	
BioReCer	Biological Resources Certifications Schemes	BioReCer aims to ensure the environmental performance and traceability of the biological feedstock used by the bio-based industries, deploying guidelines to strengthen the current certification schemes.	link
FOODCost	FOOD Costing and Internalisation of Externalities for System Transition	The project redefines the value of food and provides a set of improved and harmonised analytical instruments for the valuation and internalisation of externalities.	link
ALIGNED	Aligning life cycle assessment methods and bio-based sectors for improved environmental performance	ALIGNED will collaborate with industries and representatives from five Bio-Based Sectors: Construction, Woodworking, Textile, Pulp and Paper, And Bio-Chemicals to harmonize and advance the scientific use of LCA in the bio-based sector.	link
BIORADAR	Monitoring system of the environmental and social sustainability and circularity of industrial bio-based systems	BIORADAR aims to help organisations, policymakers and investors have the necessary information to step towards a more sustainable, bio-based economic model. It will do so by following a system perspective to fill the indicator gaps in material circularity and evaluating the environmental and social impacts of industrial bio-based systems while developing digital monitoring tools that will provide benchmarks and a self-assessment platform for bio-based industries.	link
RIBES	Regional Inclusive Biobased Entrepreneurship Solutions	RIBES aims to accelerate the adoption of bio-based innovations by developing governance and business models that integrate the principles of the circular bioeconomy, social innovation, and rural development. Focused on nine European regions, RIBES fosters collaboration among policymakers, businesses, academia, and civil society to create sustainable and inclusive bio-based value chains.	link

Sister Projects	Title	Description	Website
<i>REDOL</i>	Aragon’s regional hub for circularity	REDOL aims to elevate European Hubs for circularity by showcasing sustainable methods to harness Solid Urban Waste (SUW) through industrial-urban symbiosis (I-US) strategies. Their goal is to enhance technological, managerial, economic, and social readiness for a more sustainable future.	link
<i>EuBioNet</i>	The European Bioeconomy Network	The European Bioeconomy Network is a proactive alliance of 134 EU-funded projects and initiatives dealing with Bioeconomy promotion, communication and support.	link

Building on our previous efforts, we took strategic steps to ensure the post-project impact and continued dissemination of our results. To achieve this, all sister projects can join the LinkedIn group on Certification and Labelling Schemes for the EU Bioeconomy, providing them with a platform to stay informed about post-project activities and developments. As several consortium members have already joined the group, some of whom will be actively involved in post-project BMT developments, they will continue sharing relevant news and updates. This approach ensures that our sister projects remain engaged, stay informed about further advancements, and have the opportunity to interact and collaborate with our project partners through this dedicated group.

8. Monitoring, Evaluation and reporting framework

8.1 Monitoring and evaluation (updated)

The monitoring mechanisms were crucial in ensuring the successful implementation of the D&C strategy and achieving the DCP goals; essentially, they measured the impact of the dissemination efforts. Therefore, a monitoring process was established at the beginning of the project. This process helped identify potential gaps and challenges, the specific needs of relevant stakeholders, and best practices that could be adopted.

A set of KPIs was selected to evaluate the impact of the DCP activities. Naturally, the metric targets and needs were adjusted based on the project's results and included in the updated deliverable (M36). The dissemination manager, with support from consortium partners, tracked continuously quantitative metrics and reported them during the reporting periods.

Below is presented the list of KPIs for the dissemination and communication activities of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED along with their status:

Table 11. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED'S Key Performance Indicators

Assessed element	Metric	Target	Status (M36)
<i>Visits to SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website</i>	Nr of visits (total)	> 10,000	10,665 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Social media accounts (LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter)</i>	Nr of followers	> 1,000	1,078 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Nr. of impressions	> 30,000	40,598 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Newsletter</i>	Nr. of published Newsletters	6	6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Nr. of subscribers	> 200	206 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Network of Interest</i>	Nr. of participants	≥ 50	93 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Project workshops</i>	Nr. of workshops	≥ 10	13 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Participation to external events</i>	Nr. of events	≥ 10	27 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Promotional video</i>	Nr. of views (total)	> 500	546 views (general promotional video) 837 views (all project's videos) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

<i>Synergies with other initiatives</i>	Nr. of joint actions	10	14 sister projects / 25 joint actions <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Engagement events</i>	Nr. of events	2	3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Nr. of participants	> 50	Overall: 213 participants 77 (1st) / 55 (2nd) / 81 (3rd) participants <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project successfully achieved its Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), reflecting the effectiveness of its dissemination and communication strategy. This success was driven by the strong collaboration among project partners, who actively engaged in sharing knowledge and promoting results. Our presence at key events allowed us to connect with stakeholders and showcase the project's impact on sustainability certification. Furthermore, our active engagement on social media expanded our outreach, fostering discussions and awareness within the bio-based sector. These combined efforts ensured the project's strong visibility and long-term influence within the Horizon Europe framework.

8.2 Reporting (updated)

Confirming our initial thoughts presented in D6.1, keeping track of the dissemination, communication, and engagement activities carried out by all partners throughout the project was fundamental to its successful implementation. Therefore, reporting and documentation played a crucial role in the DCP. Throughout the project's duration, all consortium partners reported their dissemination and communication activities monthly by filling in the template provided by WHITE, which was available online in the project's repository.

After each monthly meeting, WHITE circulated a reminder to all project partners, encouraging them to complete the dissemination reporting template with the activities they had conducted. Every six months (M6, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36), WHITE consolidated the reported data and developed the semi-annual technical report for WP6.

For keeping track of the activities performed by the consortium partners, three documents have been designed and shared (Annex).

Table 12. List with Annexes for Dissemination

Annex	Dissemination Tool	Coverage	When
Annex II	Dissemination reporting template	All the dissemination activities carried out by the partners every month.	Every month
Annex III	Event's reporting template	Each single event organised by the partners or where the partners participated.	Within 30 days after the implementation of the event

Annex IV	External conferences and Events template	Any external event/conference that it is relevant to our project and with potential benefit to attend	Throughout the project (ad- hoc basis)
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Dissemination reporting template: This template recorded all dissemination and communication activities of the project. All partners updated the document on a monthly basis. Keeping track of these activities ensured that any problems or gaps were identified early, allowing for the implementation of mitigation measures to address them effectively.

Event reporting template: This template was filled out by all partners whenever they organised or participated in an event (e.g., workshop, conference, meeting, etc.). The completed template was sent to WHITE no later than 30 days after the event. Additionally, events were always communicated to WHITE in advance for promotional purposes.

The external conferences and Events template: This template facilitated the identification of events (workshops, conferences, webinars) relevant to the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED vision. Each partner filled out this template and sent the information to WHITE whenever they identified any event or conference that could be beneficial for the consortium (e.g., attending, presenting, etc.).

9. Timeline and implementation plan (updated)

The dissemination and communication activities began at the start of the project with the production of promotional material, continued with a wide range of offline and online dissemination efforts, and were completed with the promotion of the project’s final results at the project’s final event. Below are the four distinct periods during which all our dissemination and communication activities were implemented:

Figure 45. Summary of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED'S timeline

❖ First phase – early in the project (M1-M6):

During the first phase of the project, the D&C strategy was designed. As part of the strategy, several key aspects were identified, including the targeted stakeholder groups to be reached during the project and the messages to engage them. Additionally, suitable metrics for monitoring the successful implementation of the strategy were selected, and the responsibilities of the consortium partners were clearly defined. Furthermore, in addition to developing the D&C strategy, the first months of the project were dedicated to producing dissemination materials and establishing communication tools and our online presence channels. The project’s visual identity and logo, promotional materials (leaflets, posters, templates, letterheads), social media accounts (SMAs), and the project website were developed in the first 5 months. Finally, the first dissemination of the project to the broader public took place through outreach to other projects, press releases, the first newsletter, and participation in external events.

❖ Second phase – during the project (M7 - M25):

Throughout the project, constant interaction was established between the project partners and relevant stakeholders. An active community interested in the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project was created and maintained through the social media accounts (SMAs) and the project’s NoI.

Additionally, synergies were developed with other projects and initiatives relevant to the topics of bioeconomy, bio-based materials and industry, sustainability, circular economy, and certification schemes and labels. Multiple activities were planned for the second phase of the project, including dissemination events, workshops, webinars, Network of Interest meetings, joint events, and dissemination activities with sister projects. Publications and promotion of the project's results through the website and bi-annual newsletter further maximised the project's impact. Finally, the participation of consortium partners in external events and conferences, along with their connections to key networks in the sector, was leveraged to promote the project to a broader audience.

❖ **Third phase – at the end of the project (M26 - M36):**

Although the dissemination of the project's vision continued, this phase of the project mainly focused on the dissemination of its results and outcomes. In particular, towards the end of the project, the data and lessons learned enabled consortium partners to draft key policy recommendations that could support the streamlined adoption of sustainability certification schemes. The project's community (NoI, SMAs), established during the second phase, was further engaged to ensure its continuation after the project's completion. Furthermore, a final event was organised in Brussels with many EU officials invited to present the project's results and engage relevant stakeholders in the post-project exploitation of the findings and mainly the BMT.

❖ **Fourth phase – Beyond the end of the project**

As part of the ongoing dissemination efforts for the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project, several key platforms and tools will be leveraged to ensure sustained engagement and visibility. A dedicated LinkedIn group will serve as a hub for networking, knowledge sharing, and discussions on biobased products and sustainability certification, fostering collaboration among stakeholders and keeping them informed about project updates. Additionally, all project outputs, including publications and datasets, will be made publicly available through Zenodo, ensuring broad accessibility to the research and policy communities. The project website will stay active beyond the project's completion, preserving access to relevant information, deliverables, and resources. These efforts aim to extend the project's impact beyond its official duration, maintaining engagement with stakeholders and promoting the project's vision and outcomes. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium is committed to ensuring that the project's legacy reaches as many relevant stakeholders as possible, with relevant publications further disseminating its results even after the official conclusion.

10. Conclusions (updated)

Looking back at the communication and dissemination strategy, we can conclude that the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project successfully promoted its results not only to a broad audience but also to the targeted stakeholders. The dissemination activities helped raise awareness among key stakeholders about the project, made it visible within the EU community of related initiatives, and communicated its core results and tools effectively.

Throughout the project cycle, the consortium reached over 47.000 from Europe and beyond. The variety of communication materials and approaches, combined with the diverse activities, allowed the consortium to engage various target groups and ensure that the project not only met but, in some cases, exceeded the original KPIs.

Over the course of the project, the consortium organised and participated in many external, project-specific, and joint events. These activities, along with close collaborations with other relevant initiatives and projects, significantly expanded the project's outreach. Furthermore, regular updates to the project website and social media accounts, combined with biannual newsletters and the creation of new promotional materials, kept stakeholders engaged and attracted new interest.

A substantial amount of public reports and resources (number) were made available on the project website, ensuring the continued communication and sustainability of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED beyond its official conclusion. The project's website will remain accessible for **4** years after its completion in order to continue to host the important project's materials and results.

The project also fostered synergies with other initiatives, notably collaborating with the **BIOBASEDCERT Cluster**. This partnership facilitated deeper engagement with sustainability certification efforts for biobased industries, creating opportunities for mutual knowledge sharing, joint events, and the alignment of strategies. The collaboration with the BIOBASEDCERT Cluster helped broaden the project's reach and impact, further enhancing the visibility of its results.

As the project draws to a close, the final policy brief is being developed based on the experiences and lessons gathered over the course of the project. These policy recommendations will assist stakeholders and policymakers in adopting and scaling the project results across Europe. The policy briefs will be available on Zenodo and will be a valuable resource for other EU projects and researchers seeking similar materials.

Finally, the excellent collaboration among all partners and their efforts in involving stakeholders, as well as their dedication to disseminating and communicating the project's results, were key factors in achieving the success of the communication and dissemination activities.

About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. This objective is realised by the development of a monitoring system, mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products, and feasibility assessment from the adoption of certification schemes and labels considering actual economic as well as internalized environmental and social costs and benefits. The results of the project are leveraged to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. These ambitions are addressed by a strong, well-balanced and multi-disciplinary consortium comprised of 5 complementary partners. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thereby supports the development of harmonized system requirements, continuous improvement of sustainability certification schemes and labels and contributes towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral and sustainable biobased industry.

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